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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe different post-exascale technologies for plasma simulations. We focus on the quantum technologies which leverage unique quantum mechanical phenomena such as quantum superposition and entanglement and have potential to show speedup in performing certain tasks when compared to the existing classical computers. The practical realization of quantum computing is making rapid progress and therefore it is crucial to devise suitable quantum algorithms which can benefit plasma simulation problems. In this deliverable we review the existing quantum algorithms which have shown to be useful for some of the problems within the paradigm of plasma simulations.

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1 Introduction

Plasma simulations which deal with the complex interactions happening in ionized gases are some of the computationally hardest problems. Developing effective numerical techniques, and computational methods to solve some of the problems within this paradigm can benefit plethora of scientific fields such as understanding stellar atmospheres, interstellar medium, modelling space weather, understanding controlled fusion reaction for generating energy and so on. There are several computational methods to model plasma behaviour under various conditions. Kinetic models such as particle in cell (PIC) [1], and monte-carlo methods [2], magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) [3] are some of the successful models to describe plasma [4]. All these methods focus on solving the equations of motions together with Maxwell's equations for electromagnetic fields. There are several codes that have been developed and can be implemented on high performance computers (HPC) which offer large parallel processing of the codes.

There are several new computing paradigms being developed using different physical systems which offer unique advantages in speeding up computations. Among them quantum computing is a revolutionary technology which is theoretically proven to show substantial speed up in certain tasks in comparison with the existing supercomputers, which we will refer to as classical computers in this deliverable [5]. Quantum computers are built out of quantum systems whose states are described by a vector in the complex vector space called the Hilbert space (the vector space where the inner product is defined). The equation of motion of such quantum systems is described by a time dependent Schrödinger equation. Further, the dimensions of Hilbert space grows exponentially with the size of the quantum system. Classical computers are not ideal for simulating quantum systems as the computational resources scale exponentially and quantum computers have shown to be efficient for this task [6, 7, 8].

The study of quantum computing for plasma physics applications is still in its initial stage, where some of the problems in plasma physics have been identified that can be simulated on a quantum computer [9]. Most of the simulation techniques proposed so far depend on formulating a Schrödinger description of the given equations of motion of the plasma [10]. In this deliverable we make a detailed literature review of some of the useful methodologies to utilize quantum technologies for plasma simulations. Further we also briefly review other post-exascale technologies such as cryogenic computer, 3D stacked integrated circuits, photonic computing, post-silicon materials, and neuromorphic computing.

This deliverable is organized as follows: In Sec. 2, we explain the basics of quantum computing, different quantum technologies which are being developed currently. Further, we elaborate the basics of quantum computing for plasma physics with the description of quantum methodologies used for linear equations, non-linear equations, eigen modes and plasma instabilities, and quantum lattice algorithms. We also introduce the software tools that are available to perform quantum computation using quantum hardwares as well as simulators. In Sec. 3 we briefly explain the other post-exascale technologies which can benefit plasma simulation problems.

2 Quantum Computing

Quantum computing is an exciting emergent technology for solving many computationally complex problems, as quantum systems provide exponential computational resources for storing and processing information in the number of available physical qubits. One of the promising application of quantum computing has been in simulating physical systems in particular quantum systems. Given that simulation time for quantum systems scales exponentially on a classical computer, quantum computers are a natural fit for this task and can potentially outperform existing classical algorithms and show real quantum advantage.

The idea of quantum computers began in the 1980's with Feynman's proposal stressing the need of quantum computers for the purpose of quantum simulations. Further Paul Benioff's quantum turing machine, Deutsch's idea Universal quantum computers became the basis of practical realization of quantum computers. In the early 1990's Peter Shor formulated a quantum algorithm (Shor's algorithm) to find prime factors of an integer which provides exponential speed than any existing supercomputers. This was followed by the inventions of other prominent quantum algorithms such as Grover's search algorithm, and Deutsch Josza algoirithm. The earliest experimental demonstrations of quantum computer was done using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) qubits implementing Grover's search algorithm in 1998 [11]. Later on, it was showed that a large scale NMR quantum computer cannot contain entanglement which is a key property of quantum systems based on which many quantum algorithms depend. At the present, quantum computing has sought a huge attention in the academic community and industries leading to achieving several milestones such as showing quantum supremacy [12, 13].

The most famous realization of quantum computer is a gate model quantum computer that implements a quantum circuit, where an initial set of quantum bits (qubits) are subjected to linear unitary operations which are subsequently measured in the end. Various quantum algorithms can be proposed in this setup which leverage the unique properties of quantum mechanics such as quantum entanglement, quantum superposition, uncertainty principle, and quantum tunneling.

2.1 Quantum computing technologies

Qubits are the building blocks of quantum computers. They can be constructed from isolated quantum systems which can be manifested in two distinct quantum states. Naturally occurring quantum systems can be used to describe qubits such as spins of electrons, electron energy levels, or they can be manufactured, for example superconducting qubits. Although, mathematically similar equations of motion describe the dynamics of these quantum mechanical systems, each of them provide different advantage from practical point of view. In general, the feasibility of a quantum technology approach is given by DiVincenzo's criteria: 1) possibility of well characterized and scalable qubits, 2) It should be possible to initialize the qubits in the desired state multiple times, 3) qubits should have long coherent times in order to perform quantum algorithms, 4) Possibility of implementing universal set of quantum gates, 5) Presence of accurate measurement protocols of the output evolved state. Here we discuss the major quantum technologies used in present day by academic groups and industry.

2.1.1 Superconducting circuits

Superconducting qubits are the most advanced and widely used approach towards practical quantum computing [14, 15]. They are manufactured solid state circuits, and there are three major types of qubits that can be constructed using superconductors: charge qubits, flux qubits and phase qubits. The superconducting charge qubits are closed loop circuits made of superconducting reservoir (a voltage source and a capacitor) coupled to a Josephson junction (A thin insulating layer sandwiched between superconducting layers) through a superconducting island. This setup is essentially an LC circuit [16]. The presence of Josephson junction in place of a regular inductor introduces anharmonicity in the energy level solution of the cooper pairs. This makes it possible to control the quantum system to be in the ground state or the first excited state alone using microwave pulses of appropriate frequency without populating the higher energy levels, in other words construct a qubit. An additional shunt capacitance is introduced in charge qubits to form transmon qubits which decrease charge noise in the circuit leading to increased coherence times [17]. Major quantum computing companies such as IBM and Google use transmon qubits in their quantum processors. In fact, Google's sycamore quantum processor which is made of 53 transmon qubits showed quantum supremacy in finding bias in random quantum circuits [13].

Superconductors can also be used to construct flux qubits, where an external magnetic flux is applied to a superconducting loop consisting of multiple Josephson junctions [18]. The system being quantum mechanical allows certain discrete flux values and the corresponding currents in the loop. The lowest energy states of the cooper pairs flowing through clockwise and anticlockwise directions constitute qubit states.

Superconducting phase qubits are constructed with Josephson junctions which have high ratio of Josephson energy vs charge energy of the order of 10^6 (which is < 1 in the case of charge qubit and of the order of 10 in the case of flux qubit) [19]. The potential across Josephson junction can be modelled as a particle interacting with a "washer board potential" with many local minima. Each local minimum accommodates further energy levels. The two of the lowest energy levels of one of these minima is used to define a phase qubit.

2.1.2 Trapped Ions

In this quantum technology, charged particles or ions are localized in space by electromagnetic potential [20]. This technique called Paul trap implements a 3-D rotating saddle-shaped potential created by time-dependent electric fields. The energy levels of ions describe the states of the qubit and can be manipulated using photons (laser) to create single qubit operations. Further, many ions can be trapped in a chain and they are cooled to low temperatures to avoid the relative motions when an individual ion is acted with photons.

To create two distinct qubit states, one requires a ground state. Certain elements can show degenerate ground states such as Calcium-40 and the process called optimal pumping is used to make all atoms to be in one of the ground state by exciting them to a short lived higher auxiliary state. Further it is essential to have a long lived excited state, since in most cases the atoms prefer to be in the unfilled ground state. In elements such as Calcium-40 there is a presence of meta-stable states which have higher life times.

In case of Calcium-43, the energy spectrum show hyperfine structures in which case the excited states have infinite lifetimes. However, very precise techniques are required to manipulate the qubits in this case.

Two qubit gates called Mølmer-Sørensen gate can be used to create entanglement between ions which is essential to harness the power of quantum computing [21]. Trapped ions have long coherence times. IonQ and Honeywell are the major companies which are developing trapped ion quantum computers.

2.1.3 Photons

Photonic qubits also known as flying qubits move from point to the other at the speed of light and show several advantages over other qubits: they have a long coherence time, they do not interact with the environment, the gate operations are simple, and they can work at room temperatures. The simple light states known as Gaussian states can be prepared using linear materials [22]. Different operations can be performed on Gaussian states using optical elements such as waveguide, phase-shifter and beamsplitters. Unlike the qubit states described so far which have two computational bases, the Gaussian states are characterized by position and momentum bases which can take infinitely many values. The state of light is a Gaussian state if the associated Wigner function (a quasi-probability function in phase space) is a Gaussian function. Light in vacuum is a Gaussian function centred around the mean value 0. Coherent states are other examples of Gaussian states produced by lasers. The mean value of the coherent states can be displaced using displacement operators or in a lab using beam splitters. Further, they can be rotated in phase space using phase-shifters. It is also possible to change the width of the probability distribution using non-linear components to squeeze the probability distribution in one direction or to produce “squeezed states” of light. One way to encode information in them is to perform measurement of the number of photons in a Gaussian light. The photon number measurement collapses the Gaussian state into photon number state or Fock states. These Fock states are non-Gaussian states and can be used to define a photonic qubit. A Gaussian state of light can be a superposition of multiple Fock states.

To build a Universal quantum computer using non-Gaussian states, a particular class of states called GKP states have been shown to be useful. One can define a $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ qubit states out of the infinite dimensional states possible for light using GKP states. These states can be approximated by photonic circuits called Gaussian Bosonic Samplers (GBS). The photonic quantum computer Jiuzhang with large scale showed quantum supremacy in performing Gaussian Bosonic Sampling in 200 s which would have taken 2.5 billion years by any existing super computer [12]. Xanadu is a major company which builds large scale GBS based quantum computers.

2.1.4 Neutral atoms

In this approach neutral atoms are cooled and suspended in space using optical tweezers (made of highly focused laser beams) [23]. In particular, a class of atoms called Rydberg atoms are used in this technology which have electrons occupying higher energy state with a high principal quantum number. Rydberg atoms such as Rubidium-85, despite being neutral, react to electromagnetic waves by negative charge centres being pushed to the center of the laser beam and the positive charges being pushed away from the beam and

making the whole atom being fixed in a laser beam. Electronic energy levels of the atoms (ground state and first excited state) are used to encode qubits. The main advantage of this technique is that the number of qubits are highly scalable. Atom Computing is the major company building this class of quantum computing¹. Recently, the company has made an announcement to release a 1000 qubit quantum computer in the recent future which is a major milestone in the development of quantum computers.

Some other prominent quantum technological approaches include topological quantum computing [24], silicon quantum dots [25], diamond NV centers [15] and a very recent advancement of using molecules for quantum information processing [26, 27]

2.2 Basics of quantum computing for plasma simulations

Plasma simulations are some of the hardest computational problems and Quantum computing can be a useful tool to solve some of the problems in this field. The biggest challenge in harnessing quantum technologies for plasma simulations is to formulate plasma simulations as quantum mechanical problems. One common method used so far is to identify problems within the paradigm of plasma simulation which can be formulated as a differential equation similar to Schrödinger equation with a well-defined Hamiltonian so that they can be simulated on a quantum computer [28, 29, 30].

2.3 Quantum algorithms for plasma physics

One of the feasible applications of near-term quantum devices is Hamiltonian simulations. Quantum devices can perform dynamical simulation of systems whose equations of motion can be formulated as Schrödinger equation. It is a linear differential equation for wavefunction ψ of particles characterised by a Hermitian operator called Hamiltonian \hat{H} .

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \hat{H} \psi. \quad (1)$$

In the recent article by Dodin and Startsev [10], the authors have identified relevant problems within plasma physics which can benefit from quantum computing and have proposed the methodologies to solve them. Here we briefly outline the techniques proposed in [10] for linear and non-linear plasma dynamics, finding eigenmodes and plasma stability and variational approaches for solving non-linear equations. In addition, we also discuss other promising techniques such as quantum lattice algorithms and differentiable quantum circuits.

2.3.1 Linear dynamics

The Radiofrequency (RF)-wave in plasma can be represented as a Schrödinger equation [31]. For a cold collisionless plasma, the corresponding Hamiltonian is a sparse Hermitian matrix. Consider cold collisionless plasma with N species with charges e_s , masses m_s and densities $N_{0s} = n_{0s}(x)$ (x is the spatial coordinate) in the presence of

¹<https://atom-computing.com/>

electric field \mathbf{E} . The linearized equation for rescaled fluid velocity $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_s = v_s(4\pi n_{0s}m_s)^{1/2}$ (which has the same unit as \mathbf{E}) is

$$\partial_t \boldsymbol{\zeta}_s = \omega_{ps} \mathbf{E} + \boldsymbol{\zeta}_s \times \boldsymbol{\Omega}_s, \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_{ps} = e_s(4\pi n_{0s}/m_s)^{1/2}$ is the signed plasma frequency of species s . $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_s = e_s \mathbf{B}_0(s)/(m_s c)$ is the s th species gyrofrequency. \mathbf{B}_0 is the dc magnetic field and c is the speed of light. The Ampère's law and Faraday's law for this system of plasma with magnetic field \mathbf{B} are

$$\partial_t \mathbf{E} = - \sum_s \omega_{ps} \boldsymbol{\zeta}_s + c \nabla \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (3)$$

$$\partial_t \mathbf{B} = -c \nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (4)$$

Consider a vector of 3×3 Hermitian matrices, $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_x, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_y, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_z\}$,

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha}_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha}_z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

It can be shown that for any two column vectors \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , $\mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{B} = -i(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \mathcal{A})\mathcal{B}$. Equations (2), (3), and (4) and be restated as

$$i\partial_t \boldsymbol{\zeta}_s = i\omega_{ps} \mathbf{E} - (\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}_s) \boldsymbol{\zeta}_s, \quad (6)$$

$$i\partial_t \mathbf{E} = -i \sum_s \omega_{ps} \boldsymbol{\zeta}_s + ic(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \mathbf{B}, \quad (7)$$

$$i\partial_t \mathbf{B} = -ic(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \mathbf{E}, \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = -i\nabla$. The above equations can be written as the vector equation of the form (1), with $\psi = (8\pi)^{-1/2} \{\boldsymbol{\zeta}_1, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_N, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}\}$ which is dimension $3(N+2)$. The corresponding time-independent Hermitian Hamiltonian is

$$\hat{H} = \begin{pmatrix} -\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}_1(x) & 0 & \dots & 0 & i\omega_{p1}(x) & 0 \\ 0 & -\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}_2(x) & \dots & 0 & i\omega_{p1}(x) & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}_N(x) & i\omega_{pN}(x) & 0 \\ -i\omega_{p1}(x) & -i\omega_{p1}(x) & \dots & -i\omega_{pN}(x) & 0 & i\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -i\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

This Hamiltonian is sparse and therefore an efficient Quantum Hamiltonian Simulation is possible using the existing quantum devices. The relevant measurements such as energy density can be computed from the measurement outcome of such Hamiltonian simulations.

In addition, the authors in [10] have also considered plasma with inhomogeneous density and finite temperature. In this case the Hamiltonian is of pseudo-Hermitian kind ($\hat{H}^\dagger \hat{\eta} = \hat{\eta} \hat{H}$, where $\hat{\eta}$ is a time independent Hermitian operator.) It is possible to solve such equations as initial value problem or boundary value problems as RF-waves form stationary waves within some boundaries. Kinetic waves simulation can also be done using this approach. In particular, for collisionless kinetic model where background plasma is homogeneous and isotropic, Schrödinger representation is possible with Hermitian Hamiltonian in this case. However, the matrix is not sparse and some of the techniques to perform QHS for arbitrary sparse Hamiltonian are given in [32, 33, 34].

2.3.2 Non-linear dynamics

Several phenomena within the paradigm of Plasma physics are non-linear. Simulating non-linear dynamics using quantum algorithms is tricky as quantum mechanics is inherently linear. Here we briefly elaborate some of the quantum techniques that have been proposed so far for solving non-linear equations as elaborated in [10]. Consider a generic ordinary differential equation

$$\dot{u} = g(t, u), \quad (10)$$

where u is a vector $\{u^1, u^2, \dots, u^{d_u}\}$, and g is a non-linear vector function $g \equiv \{g^1, g^2, \dots, g^{d_u}\}$. For a simple non-linearity $g \propto u^2$, one can encode the variable u in the amplitude of a given quantum state $|\psi\rangle = \sum_i \psi_i |i\rangle$ and evolve it to a state with quadratic amplitude to mimic a non-linear evolution in quantum state amplitude.

$$|\psi'\rangle = \sum_{ijk} A_{ijk} \psi_j \psi_k |i\rangle \quad (11)$$

This non linear transformation of $|\psi\rangle \rightarrow |\psi'\rangle$ is a difficult task using one qubit because of linear nature of quantum evolution and no-cloning theorem of quantum information. This can be achieved by a unitary transformation $e^{-i\epsilon\hat{H}}$ (where $\epsilon \ll 1$) of two copies of ψ and an ancilla qubit ψ_P which is initialized in the state $|0\rangle_P$. A Hermitian Hamiltonian operator which can be used to create such transformation is given by

$$\hat{H} = -i\hat{A} \otimes |1\rangle_P \langle 0|_P + i\hat{A}^\dagger \otimes |0\rangle_P \langle 1|_P, \quad (12)$$

where \hat{A} is a non-Hermitian operator,

$$\hat{A} = \sum_{ijk} A_{ijk} |i, 0\rangle \langle j, k|, \quad (13)$$

and the action of \hat{A} on a state $|\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle$ is given by

$$\hat{A}|\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle = \left(\sum_{ijk} A_{ijk} \psi_i \psi_j |i\rangle \right) |0\rangle \quad (14)$$

Therefor the unitary transformation is given by

$$e^{-i\epsilon\hat{H}}|\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle|0\rangle_P \approx |\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle|0\rangle_P + \epsilon\hat{A}|\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle|1\rangle_P. \quad (15)$$

One can measure the ancilla qubit of this transformed quantum state with the post-selection of $|1\rangle_P$ state to obtain the quadratic amplitude with the probability ϵ^2 . This algorithm is suitable when g is a polynomial function of lower order. Further, at each iteration of encoding non-linearity, the number of copies of quantum states required scales exponentially. Another general approach to solve non-linear equations is to linearize them. In [10] authors have described the linearization of a system classical Hamiltonian equations and Stochastic equations.

2.3.3 Variational approaches

Variational quantum algorithms (VQAs) have gained major attention in recent times which leverage hybrid classical-quantum techniques and are very well suited for near term quantum devices applications. In general, variational quantum algorithms involve preparing a variational ansatz $\phi(\theta)$, θ are classical variational parameters and approximate it to a desired state (usually ground state) by minimizing the cost function of the output such as energy. The cost function evaluation is done on the quantum computer, while the optimization is done on a classical computer. Consider a general differential equation $\partial_t \psi = \hat{O}(t)\psi$. Suppose at time t_n the solution of the equation is approximated by the variational ansatz, $\phi(\theta_n) \approx \psi(t_n)$. Then, at time $t_{n+1} = t_n + \tau$, the approximate solution $\psi(t_{n+1})$ is given by

$$\psi(t_{n+1}) \approx [I + \tau \hat{O}(t_n)]\psi(t_n) \approx [\mathbf{I} + \tau \hat{O}(t_n)]\phi(\theta_n). \quad (16)$$

If the term $\hat{O}(t_n)\phi(\theta_n)$ has polynomial dependence on $\phi(\theta_n)$, then multiple copies of $\phi(\theta_n)$ can be created and amplitude encoding method described in 2.3.2 can be used to generate the non-polynomial terms and for linear system of equations. Therefore, a cost function that can be evaluated to find an approximate solution $\phi(\theta_{n+1})$ at time t_{n+1} is

$$C(\theta_{n+1}) = \|\phi(\theta_{n+1}) - \psi(t_{n+1})\|^2 \approx \|\phi(\theta_{n+1}) - [I + \tau \hat{O}(t_n)]\phi(\theta_n)\|^2. \quad (17)$$

Variational quantum algorithms which rely on parametrized quantum circuits that can essentially be trained for machine learning tasks. In particular, differential quantum circuits has proven to be useful in solving differential equations. We will discuss more about it in detail in Sec. 2.3.5

2.3.4 Eigenmodes and plasma stability

Linear ideal magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) is used to model the stability of magnetically confined plasma. The plasma displacement from equilibrium is similar to a general eigenvalue equation of the form $\hat{H}\psi = \lambda\psi$ [35], and is given by

$$F(\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{x})) = -\omega^2 \rho(\mathbf{x})\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (18)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ is the displacement vector from the equilibrium, $\rho(\mathbf{x})$ is the mass density of plasma. F is the linear force operator which is Hermitian. In [35], authors have shown to use quantum phase estimation algorithm to solve this general eigenvalue equation with

$$\psi = \rho(\mathbf{x})\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \hat{H} = F(\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{x})). \quad (19)$$

Variational quantum eigensolvers which use classical-quantum hybrid techniques can also be used to solve this equation using near-term quantum devices, analogous to the technique described in 2.3.3. An ansatz state $\phi(\theta)$ of classical parameters θ can be prepared on a quantum computer and the energy expectation value of this ansatz for a given Hamiltonian \hat{H} , $\langle \phi(\theta) | \hat{H} | \phi(\theta) \rangle$ is computed and it is minimized over the classical parameters θ . The Hamiltonian can be split into sum of simple operators, for example Pauli spin operators whose expectation value is easy to compute. The next eigenvalues can be computed by minimizing the energy expectation value in the subspace orthogonal to $\phi(\theta)$.

2.3.5 Differentiable quantum circuits

Differentiable quantum circuits is a quantum machine learning approach to solving differential equations. There are mainly two ways of solving differential equations through numerical methods. One of them is to discretize the variable space and use finite difference methods. The other way is to approximate the solutions to the differential equations using appropriate basis functions and optimizing the coefficients. In this section, we outline the methods developed in [36], where the authors resort to the latter. The algorithm proposed in this article is analogous to the physics informed neural networks which is a popular scientific machine learning approach in recent times. Here the authors optimize the variational parameters to match target function values at certain grid points, derivative of the function at certain points and also the boundary conditions.

The quantum neural network with a fixed number of initial qubits in state $|\psi\rangle_{in}$ undergoes a unitary transformation $\hat{U}_\phi(x)$ corresponding to quantum feature mapping. This step facilitates encoding of classical information x by using suitable mappings such as Fourier transform or Chebyshev transforms. Following this, a suitable variational ansatz \hat{U}_θ is chosen whose parameters are optimized to obtain the approximate solution. The initial qubits in the parametrized quantum circuit undergo the transformation to the final state,

$$|f_{\theta,\phi}(x)\rangle = \hat{U}_\theta \hat{U}_\phi |\psi\rangle_{in}. \quad (20)$$

Further, the derivative circuit is computed which requires the differentiation of the feature map $\hat{U}_\phi(x)$. This is done by automatic differentiation techniques [37]. Once the variational circuit and the derivative circuit are constructed, an appropriate Hermitian operator \hat{C} is chosen to define cost function from the readout of measurement values to approximate the solution to the equation,

$$f(x) = \langle f_{\theta,\phi}(x) | \hat{C} | f_{\theta,\phi}(x) \rangle, \quad (21)$$

where \hat{C} can be the total magnetization of the system $\hat{C} = \sum_i Z_i$. This cost function evaluation is done on the quantum hardware for a given set of parameters θ, ϕ . In addition, to evaluate the derivative circuit, it is crucial to find the derivative of the feature mapping. This is done by expressing the derivative of the unitary \hat{U}_ϕ as the sum of modified quantum operations $\hat{U}_{[\phi, \cdot]}$. The cost function approximating the derivative quantum circuits can be evaluated using parameter shift rule.

$$df(x)/dx = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \left(\langle f_{d\phi,j,\theta}^+(x) | \hat{C} | f_{d\phi,j,\theta}^+(x) \rangle - \langle f_{d\phi,j,\theta}^-(x) | \hat{C} | f_{d\phi,j,\theta}^-(x) \rangle \right), \quad (22)$$

with $|f_{d\phi,j,\theta}^\pm(x)\rangle$ is defined using parameter shift rule [38], and j corresponds to the individual quantum operations involved in quantum feature map encoding. A loss function accounting how close the trial function evaluates the solution to the given differential equation at grid points, differential of the function at those grid points, and match the boundary conditions. Specifically in [36], authors construct the loss function,

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta[d_x f, f, x] = \mathcal{L}_\theta^{(\text{diff})}[d_x f, f, x] + \mathcal{L}_\theta^{(\text{boundary})}[f, x], \quad (23)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_\theta^{(\text{diff})}[d_x f, f, x]$ and $\mathcal{L}_\theta^{(\text{boundary})}[f, x]$ are the distance functions between the actual value and the predicted values for differential equations and boundary conditions respectively. The distance function can be chosen to be any appropriate function such as mean squared error (MSE) or mean absolute errors (MAE). The loss function can be optimized using any classical optimization techniques. These steps are repeated until an exit condition is satisfied such as the number of iterations or by specifying the minimum loss function, the algorithm has to reach. With this approach of differentiable quantum circuits, the authors have shown to produce impressive results for different classes of differential equations such as ordinary differential equations, strongly coupled equations, and the equations in fluid dynamics such as Navier-Stokes equation.

2.3.6 Quantum lattice algorithm

Quantum lattice algorithms (QLAs) are used to model electromagnetic wave propagation using interleaved unitary collision and streaming operators which in the continuum limit represent the differential equations of interest. The time evolution under such unitary operation is given by,

$$\psi(t + \Delta t) = \Pi\psi(t), \quad (24)$$

where Π is a product operator composed of collision operators \hat{C} and streaming operator \hat{S} . QLAs were first used to solve Dirac equation [39]. This algorithm can be implemented using qubits on a quantum computer as lattice points and the streaming and collision operators can be modeled using quantum gates. The collision operators create the entanglement between these qubits and streaming operators propagate the entanglement. Quantum lattice algorithms have been used for plethora of problems which include Maxwell's equation in vacuum and dielectric media [40, 41], modelling solitons [42, 43, 44], 2-spin Bose-Einstein condensates [45], fluid dynamics simulations [46] and so on. Here we briefly describe the ideas behind modelling Maxwell's equations in a material media using QLAs by representing them as Dirac's equation as proposed in [40].

Consider Maxwell's equation for linear isotropic material,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \rho(\mathbf{x}, t), \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= 0 \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t}, \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{-\partial \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mu(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ with ε and μ being permittivity and permeability of the medium respectively.

To reformulate Maxwell's equation in the form of Dirac's equation, authors in [40] introduce the Riemann–Silberstein vectors for the two polarizations of the electromagnetic fields

$$F^\pm = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\sqrt{\varepsilon} \mathbf{E} \pm \frac{\mathbf{B}}{\sqrt{\mu}} \right]. \quad (26)$$

Further, it can be shown that for a homogeneous medium the Maxwell's equation can be

rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{pmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{pmatrix} q_2 \\ q_3 \\ q_0 \\ q_1 \end{pmatrix} + i\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \begin{pmatrix} q_2 \\ q_3 \\ -q_0 \\ -q_1 \end{pmatrix} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \begin{pmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ -q_2 \\ -q_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

where the 4-spinor components are defined as

$$\begin{pmatrix} -F_x^+ + iF_y^+ \\ F_z^+ \\ F_z^+ \\ F_x^+ + iF_y^+ \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

These 4-components can be described by quantum states of 4 qubits. Maxwell's equations Eq. (27) are similar to Dirac's equation for massless particle for which QLA is well formulated [39]. One can observe that in Eq. (27) there is a coupling between the qubits $q_0 \leftrightarrow q_2$, and $q_1 \leftrightarrow q_3$. Consider the collision operators which entangle these pairs of qubits,

$$C_X = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & \sin \theta & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & 0 & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & -\sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}, C_Y = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & i \sin \theta & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & 0 & i \sin \theta \\ i \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & i \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

The 1D unitary streaming operators advances the given qubit state by one lattice point, i.e., $S_{\pm X}^n q_n(x, y, t) \rightarrow q_n(x \pm 1, y, t)$. The streaming operators $S_{\pm X}^{01}$ which acts on qubits q_0 and q_1 , keeping q_2 and q_3 fixed and similarly $S_{\pm X}^{01}$ which acts on q_2 and q_3 leaving q_0 and q_1 fixed. The interleaved collision operators for x and y dimensions, and for both directions can be separately treated as

$$U_X = S_{-X}^{01} C_X S_{+X}^{01} C_X^\dagger \cdot S_{+X}^{23} C_X S_{-X}^{23} C_X^\dagger \quad (30)$$

$$U_X^{adj} = S_{+X}^{01} C_X^\dagger S_{-X}^{01} C_X \cdot S_{-X}^{23} C_X^\dagger S_{+X}^{23} C_X,$$

$$U_Y = S_{-Y}^{23} C_Y S_{+Y}^{23} C_Y^\dagger \cdot S_{+Y}^{01} C_Y S_{-Y}^{01} C_Y^\dagger \quad (31)$$

$$U_Y^{adj} = S_{+Y}^{23} C_Y^\dagger S_{-Y}^{23} C_Y \cdot S_{-Y}^{01} C_Y^\dagger S_{+Y}^{01} C_Y.$$

With these interleaved operators, the QLA time advancement of 4-spinor components can be generated as

$$\begin{pmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix}_{t+\delta t} = U_Y^{adj} U_Y U_X^{adj} U_X \begin{pmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix}_t \quad (32)$$

This equation yields the 2D Maxwell's equations in $x - y$ dimensions

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{pmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{pmatrix} q_2 \\ q_3 \\ q_0 \\ q_1 \end{pmatrix} + i\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \begin{pmatrix} q_2 \\ q_3 \\ -q_0 \\ -q_1 \end{pmatrix} + O(\varepsilon^2), \quad (33)$$

provided that the time advancement scaling is $\delta t \varepsilon^2$ and lattice spacing $\delta x = \delta y \varepsilon$ and the collision angle $\theta = \varepsilon/4$.

2.4 Programming quantum algorithms

At present, there are several quantum cloud computing platforms which allow to program their quantum simulators and quantum processors. Many of the companies offering these services also provide open-source software to easily run quantum computing experiments on quantum hardware or simulators. Here we list some of such quantum computing platforms:

Qiskit IBM's Qiskit is an open-source software tool to program IBM's quantum computers and simulators [47]. It is a user-friendly platform which allows one to build circuits, compile, and analyze results with simple python codes. The basic package of Qiskit is Qiskit Terra which helps to define the number of qubits, the gates and visualize the circuits. Further Qiskit is supported by the state vector simulator and unitary simulator from the Qiskit-Aer backend. Qiskit-Aer also allows to simulate different realistic noise models such as amplitude damping, phase damping and so on. Qiskit has packages to perform various quantum computing applications such as variational quantum algorithms, quantum optimization, and quantum machine learning

Cirq This library is by Google's Quantum AI which helps to build quantum circuits including many textbook examples of variational quantum algorithms which have feasible applications in the Noisy intermediate scale quantum era². Further, TensorFlow quantum is a software library for quantum machine learning applications which leverage Google's quantum computing resources. OpenFermion by Google is an open source software tool to simulate fermionic system such as those in quantum chemistry problems.

PennyLane PennyLane is an open-source software library developed by Xanadu focused on quantum machine learning and quantum chemistry applications [48]. PennyLane allows the development of differentiable quantum circuits, which means it allows quantum computers to compute gradients and optimize with respect to trainable parameters which is the building block of machine learning techniques such as deep learning. PennyLane is also integrated with high performance computing resources such as those by NVIDIA CuQuantum.

3 Other post-exascale technologies

3.1 Neuromorphic Computing

Neuromorphic computing is a computing paradigm taking inspiration from the structure and functionality of the human brain [49]. It seeks to design hardware and software that mimic the brain's neural networks, enabling machines to process information in a way that resembles human cognition. Neuromorphic computing is known for its potential in parallel processing and energy efficiency, making it an intriguing candidate for various scientific simulations, including plasma simulations. One of the most famous implementations of neuromorphic computing is IBM's TrueNorth [50]. TrueNorth is a neuromorphic chip

²<https://quantumai.google/>

Post-exascale technology	Description	Advantages relevant to plasma simulations
Quantum computing	Built from quantum mechanical systems; uses quantum superposition and entanglement as resource in quantum algorithms	Quantum Hamiltonian Simulation for solving linear equations, variational algorithms for nonlinear equation solutions
Neuromorphic computing	hardware designed inspired from human brain cognition	highly parallel computing, enhanced pattern recognition, adaptability to learn from new data
3D stacked integrated circuits	Multiple layers of integrated circuits are stacked in 3D in contrast to the traditional 2D architecture	High Bandwidth Memory (HBM) for fast memory access; lower power consumption; reduction in data transfer latency; increase memory bandwidth
Cryogenic computing	Computing using materials at extremely low temperatures	Energy efficient hardwares for HPC, and therefore faster simulations
Photonic computing	Silicon photonics to generate and process light signals	fast data transfer, low power consumption
Post-silicon materials	post-semiconductor materials such as carbon nano tubes (CNT) with enhances electrical and thermal properties	low power consumption if integrated with HPC environment

Table 1: Future technologies and their relevance to plasma simulations

designed to emulate the structure and function of the human brain. It features a massive number of artificial neurons and synapses, which are interconnected in a way that allows it to process information in a highly parallel and efficient manner. This architecture has been applied to various cognitive computing tasks, including autonomous vehicle control, natural language processing, and video games control and has gained attention for its potential in scientific and computational applications [51].

The brain-inspired architecture of neuromorphic systems can be leveraged for pattern recognition in plasma data. It can identify and track complex patterns or anomalies within the simulation data, aiding researchers in understanding and predicting plasma behaviors. In addition, Neuromorphic systems can adapt to changing conditions and learn from the simulation data. This adaptability can be valuable when studying dynamic and evolving plasma phenomena.

3.2 3D Stacked Integrated Circuits

3D Stacked Integrated Circuits represent an approach to semiconductor technology involving stacking multiple layers of integrated circuits on top of each other, as opposed to the traditional 2D planar arrangement. This innovative design significantly enhances computing performance, reduces physical footprint, and improves energy efficiency, making it an attractive solution for a wide range of applications, including plasma simulations. One of the most famous implementations of 3D Stacked Integrated Circuits is High Bandwidth Memory (HBM), investigated in Plasma-PEPSC WP5. HBM places multiple DRAM (Dynamic Random-Access Memory) layers on top of the logic die housing the compute units (example, CPU or GPU), providing significantly faster memory access speeds, lower power consumption, and a compact form factor. Stacking memory layers on top of processing units can significantly reduce data transfer latency and increase the memory bandwidth, a critical factor in large-scale plasma simulations.

3.3 Cryogenic computers

Cryogenic computing is an emerging technology that involves the operation of computing devices and components at extremely low temperatures, typically close to absolute zero Kelvin. This approach takes advantage of the properties of materials at cryogenic temperatures to improve the performance and energy efficiency of computing systems. One of the most famous implementations of cryogenic computing is the Cryogenic Electronics developed by IBM ³. This system combines superconducting qubits for quantum computing with classical computing elements, all operated at extremely low temperatures. The system showcases the potential of cryogenic computing by demonstrating the ability to harness superconducting electronics for quantum processing while maintaining connectivity to traditional, room-temperature electronics. In particular this hybrid approach allows for quantum error correction and classical computation to coexist seamlessly within a single system.

Operating electronic components at cryogenic temperatures significantly reduces energy consumption. In plasma simulations, where large-scale computations are often re-

³<https://research.ibm.com/projects/cryogenic-electronics>

quired, this can lead to substantial energy savings, making it an attractive option for sustainable HPC.

3.4 Photonic Computing

Photonic computing is a computing field that leverages the unique properties of photons (particles of light) for information processing and computation [52]. Differently from traditional electronic computing, which relies on electrons, photonic computing uses light waves to carry and process data. This technology offers several advantages, including high-speed data transfer, energy efficiency, and the potential for parallel processing. One of the most well-known implementations of photonic computing is Silicon Photonics. Silicon Photonics combines silicon-based optical components with conventional electronic circuits, enabling the generation, transmission, and detection of light signals on a silicon chip. This approach has gained popularity due to its compatibility with existing semiconductor fabrication processes and its ability to integrate optical and electronic functions on the same platform. Photonic computing can transmit data at the speed of light, facilitating the transfer of large datasets generated during plasma simulations. This capability could be critical for real-time or near-real-time data analysis and visualization. Photonics consumes significantly less power than traditional electronic circuits, making it suitable for HPC. Finally, photonic components can serve as high-speed interconnects between different computational elements, such as CPUs, GPUs, or custom accelerators.

3.5 Post-Silicon Materials

Post-Silicon Materials refer to a class of materials that are being explored as alternatives to traditional silicon in semiconductor technology. These materials offer unique properties, such as superior conductivity, higher electron mobility, and novel physical characteristics, which make them promising candidates for future computing hardware. One of the most famous implementations of post-silicon materials is the use of carbon nanotubes (CNTs). CNTs are cylindrical nanostructures made of carbon atoms arranged in a hexagonal lattice. They have extraordinary electrical and thermal properties, including high electron mobility and excellent thermal conductivity. Carbon nanotubes and other post-silicon materials have low power dissipation and can operate at higher frequencies, making them energy-efficient alternatives. Therefore integrating post-silicon materials in HPC environments can be beneficial for complex simulations including plasma simulations.

4 Conclusion

In this deliverable we have reviewed the post-exascale computing techniques useful for plasma simulations focusing on quantum technologies. The benefits of developing numerical techniques and codes for plasma simulations using quantum computing is twofold. Plasma simulations offer a novel class of computationally hard problems to be solved on quantum computers given that quantum computers are making tremendous progress towards practical applications. Plasma simulations can also benefit from potential quantum speedups with the development of appropriate quantum algorithms.

The progress done so far in terms of quantum technologies based on different physical systems, quantum algorithms, and quantum programming platforms offer a great base to build better quantum tools for plasma problems. Linear problems are much easier to be simulated on a quantum computer as quantum mechanical processes are linear. However, several problems within plasma physics are inherently non-linear and therefore there is a necessity to develop efficient algorithms to exploit the power of quantum computing for plasma problems. There has already been progresses made in this regard as well using variational quantum algorithms. For example, in [53] authors have used multiple copies of quantum states and have used tensor product states to solve non-linear differential equations. Another variational approach of using differentiable quantum circuits in [36] and explained more in detail in 2.3.5.

We have also discussed other emergent technologies which can be beneficial for plasma simulations. A great deal of energy consumption optimization can be done using novel techniques such as cryogenic computing, photonic computing, carbon nano tubes, and 3D stacked integrated circuits. Neuromorphic computing with enhanced capability to recognize patterns can aid machine learning approaches to plasma simulations. HPCs can benefit also from fast data transfer assisted with 3D stacked integrated circuits and photonic computing. We have summarized the applications of different technologies in the table 1. This deliverable addresses the central objective task 2.3 of the Plasma-PEPSC: Reviewing the role of post-exascale technologies such as quantum computing and other emergent technologies for the algorithm and software development for plasma simulations. The task of investigating the integration of these approaches into traditional HPC codes as hybrid models and HPC infrastructure will be carried out starting 2024. In addition, the efforts towards implementing one or more future technologies mentioned in the deliverable will be made in the next part of the project.

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